

Radiochemical and Thermal Studies of the Cation-Exchanged Forms of Synthetic Zeolite Linde Sieve A

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The compositions of the cobalt and silver-exchanged forms of synthetic zeolite Linde Sieve A have been determined by radiochemical and TGA studies and correspond to $\text{Co}_6\text{A} \cdot 19.8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ag}_{1.2}\text{A} \cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively ($\text{A} = \text{Al}_{12}\text{Si}_{12}\text{O}_{48}^{12-}$). Heating these zeolites inhibits their capacity for cation exchange and water absorption. No evidence of occluded NaAlO_2 has been found.

LINDE Molecular Sieve 4A is a synthetic zeolite having no counterpart in nature whose composition was given by Breck et al¹. However, Barrer and Meier² found evidence of occluded NaAlO_2 in the structure, thereby suggesting a different composition. Other workers³ have also determined the anionic framework structure and the positions of some of the counterions in the zeolite.

The present work is based on the author's studies of the cation-exchange behaviour of the zeolite 4A with Co^{+2} and Ag^{+1} by Szilard-Chalmers reactions and the thermal stabilities of these exchanged forms by TGA and DSC.

Experimental

The synthetic zeolite employed in this work was supplied by the Union Carbide International Company, U. S. A. and had a lot number 440522. The sample of the zeolite, obtained from a bulk supply, and its cation-exchanged forms were prepared by the method reported by Barrer, Rees and Ward⁴. The chemicals used were

of AnalaR quality. Cobaltous chloride ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and silver nitrate were used for preparing the cation-exchanged forms. The zeolite and its cobalt and silver-exchanged forms were irradiated to produce sodium-24, cobalt-60 and silver 110m by (n, γ) reactions. The conditions for irradiation and the results of radiochemical studies have been tabulated below (Table 1). The detectors used were Nuclear Enterprise 8312 Automatic Beta Gamma Spectrometer and Princeton Gamma-Tech. Ge(Li) Detector (Model LGC 4.5 SD) using data presentation units like memory unit model 291, display unit model 292 and control unit model 293.

Dupont TGA and DSC set-ups and Stanton Redcroft TG-750 thermobalance with Perkin-Elmer recorder 56 were used for thermal studies of the zeolites.

In order to investigate the thermal stabilities of the cation-exchanged zeolites, the cobalt and silver zeolites were heated to 650° and 1000° in a calibrated furnace for 12 hr. and equilibrated with water vapour over saturated NH_4Cl aq. at room temperature. The pre-heated and equilibrated samples were subjected to TGA. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1. CONDITIONS OF IRRADIATION : POWER ; 100Kw ; POSITION : ICIS ; NEUTRON FLUX : 1.3×10^{12} NEUTRONS/CM²/SEC

Zeolite	Standard	Isotope	Half-life	Max. beta energies per MeV	Main gamma per MeV	Composition _{1,2} - A = $\text{Al}_{12}\text{Si}_{12}\text{O}_{48}$
Sodium A	Na_2CO_3	Sodium-24	15 hrs.	1.39	1.37, 2.75	$\text{Na}_{1.2}\text{A} \cdot 27\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Cobalt A	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cobalt-60	5.3 yrs.	0.31	1.17, 1.33	$\text{Co}_6\text{A} \cdot 19.8\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Silver A	AgNO_3	Silver-110m	253 days	0.09, 0.53 ;	0.66, 0.88	$\text{Ag}_{1.2}\text{A} \cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$

The irradiation times were 5, 15 and 5 min for sodium, cobalt and silver zeolites respectively.

TABLE 2. DATA OBTAINED ON STANTON REDCROFT TG-750 THERMOBALANCE (CHART SPEED : 10MM/MINUTE ; ΔT : 30° MIN ; RECORDER RANGE : 5 MILLIVOLTS)

Zeolite	Total Weight Loss %
Cobalt A	26.0
Cobalt A heated to 650° and equilibrated over water vapour	18.9
Cobalt A " " 1000° " " " "	1.5
Silver A	15.6
Silver A heated to 650° and equilibrated over water vapour	13.5
Silver A " " 1000° " " " "	0.0

Discussion

The TGA and DSC curves for cobalt zeolite are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The DSC record shows a distinct endotherm at 102° with shoulders

Fig. 1. TGA of Cobalt Zeolite in an atmosphere of nitrogen on a DUPONT TGA set up.

Fig. 2. DSC of Cobalt Zeolite predried at $\approx 110^\circ$ and in an atmosphere of nitrogen on a DUPONT set up.

around 155° and 205°. TGA has only one major weight loss step with a highest rate of weight loss around 100°.

The cobalt zeolite, preheated at 650 and 1000 reabsorbs water after equilibration over saturated NH_4Cl (18.9 and 1.5% respectively). Complete breakdown of crystal lattice takes place beyond 1000°. This is confirmed by the cation-exchange behaviour with NH_4^+ . The sample preheated at 1000 and above shows 0% exchange when treated with a saturated solution of NH_4Cl . The TGA of the sample heated above 1000° shows a straight line without evidence of water loss. The silver zeolite, preheated at 1000° loses its crystallinity totally and cannot absorb any water even after prolonged equilibration over saturated NH_4Cl . The exchange with NH_4^+ (0%) confirms this. The sample preheated at 650° shows some 50% exchange with NH_4^+ .

The radiochemical analyses of the sodium zeolite and its exchanged forms do not show the presence of occluded Na^+ . The compositions based on the analyses of sodium, cobalt and silver contents correspond to those reported in Table 1.

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